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April 2025

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ONWUBIKO, EMMANUEL CHIDIADI, "Artificial Intelligence in Special Libraries in Africa for Selective Dissemination of Information: Any Need?" (2025). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 8261. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/8261>

Artificial Intelligence in Special Libraries in Africa for Selective Dissemination of Information: Any Need?

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Abstract

The study applied a descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 48 special librarians selected through purposive sampling techniques from 24 special libraries in Africa. The study was guided by four research objectives. The main instrument used for data collection was a 4-point questionnaire with 1 = "strongly disagree" and 4 = "strongly agree". The instrument was validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria and further subjected to internal consistency test using Cronbach's alpha. The result was coefficient $\alpha=.80$, showing that the instrument was reliable. Data administration and collection were digitally done via email with a link to the online surveys. Included in the email was a brief statement about the purpose of the study and information regarding ethical considerations. The questionnaires were completed and returned 100%. Data collected were analyzed through descriptive statistics using frequencies, percentiles and statistical mean. The outcome of the study did reveal, among other things, that there is a need for AI to be used for SDI in special libraries in Africa and that there are ways special libraries in Africa can leverage AI to enhance SDI services. Based on the findings, recommendations were made, which include that inasmuch as AI can enhance SDI in special libraries in Africa, special librarians and staff of special libraries in Africa must also be mindful of the ethical implications of using AI in SDI service delivery and take steps to protect the privacy and ownership of data and that special libraries should proceed with caution and consider its potential negative impact. By being mindful of these concerns and taking steps to mitigate them by ensuring that AI is used in a responsible and ethical manner that benefits both the library and users as well as that special libraries in Africa should come together to establish African Special Libraries Consortium (ASLC) with which they can

bargain collectively and aggressively reduced costs for the libraries access to AI technology, share their thoughts and experiences in the utilization of AI technology in general service and SDI in particular as well as exchange of ideas and skills.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Special Library, Selective Dissemination of Information, Librarians, Information and Communication Technology, Africa

1.0. Introduction

By all standards, a special library is special as it is meant to serve circumscribed users whose duty is to work exclusively for their own personal development, which will lead to the realization of the vision and mission of the parent body. The implication is that every special library is stocked with information materials and other resources in tandem with the objectives and mission of the particular organization or establishment that is the sole financier or sponsor. So, information materials and resources in this type of library are the reserve of the staff of such organization that, by extension, uses the library to satisfy their information needs with a view to being well equipped to excel in their assigned responsibilities or duties. In other words, a special library involves a selective collection primarily for a circumscribed need. Its major purpose, therefore, is to provide each of its users with the information they need at the time they need it through using the user profile. A special library is mainly involved in the selective dissemination of information (SDI) and current awareness services (CAS) (Onwubiko, 2020).

A concept rooted in science and information technology and aims to filter and deliver relevant content to users in an efficient manner (Connor,1967), selective dissemination of information (SDI) is posited as an automatic and targeted distribution of information about individuals based on their specific interests and preferences (Saeidnia, 2022), The whole idea behind the development of SDI systems is to deal with the increasing volume of information available and offer personalized information retrieval and delivery services to teeming users in an era where information is growing in an astronomical proportion and has become the prime factor of production

and development. Going the memory lane, it is on record that the first known application of SDI dates back to the 1960s, with major contributions from the online information retrieval community. Institutions such as the US National Library of Medicine (NLM) began experiments using computer systems to automatically disseminate selective information to interested users. One of the most famous and influential systems was the Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System (MEDLARS), introduced by the NLM in 1964 (Dee, 2007). MEDLARS allowed users to define their areas of interest; the system would subsequently notify the stakeholders about new articles matching their criteria.

This innovative approach was a significant advance in providing personalized information to the scientific community. With the advent of the Internet and the World Wide Web, SDI has much evolved (Saeidnia, Ghorbi, Kozak, & Abdoli, 2022). As more information became available online, new techniques and technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) were developed to support efficient filtering and targeted information delivery (Kim, Shin, Bae, Oh, Park, del Pobil, 2020 & Massis, 2018). Innovative platforms integrate various intelligent algorithms, user profiling technique lines and automated notifications to increase the effectiveness of SDI systems. Today, the concept of SDI has expanded the library beyond research and academia (Saeidnia, 2023). Inasmuch as SDI is used in business environments, social media platforms, news gathering and recommender systems, it is more pronounced in special libraries and with the invention and use of artificial intelligence, special libraries have this comparative advantage as it is believed that with AI the services of SDI will definitely be greatly enhanced by leveraging AI technologies and algorithms. It is in light of the above and the dearth of literature in this field of knowledge in this part of the globe that this study became imperative with a view to closing this gap and creating the necessary awareness. In this study, the aim is to ascertain whether AI is needed in Special libraries in \Africa for SDI and whether SDI services can be greatly enhanced by leveraging AI technologies and algorithms.

This study, therefore, is a survey on the need for AI technologies application in special libraries in Africa in consideration of notable in-fractions in their services ranging from inability to meet users' information needs to inadequate staffing, among other shortfalls

which this study intends to ascertain and how SDI performances in special libraries in Africa can be enhanced with the use of AI technologies and algorithms.

The main objectives of this study include:

- I. To determine whether AI technology applications are needed in special libraries in Africa,
- II. To ascertain how AI can be used to enhance SDI services in special libraries in Africa.
- III. To identify ethical challenges to be considered while applying AI to enhance SDI in special libraries in Africa and
- IV. Ascertain how identified ethical challenges can be mitigated.

2.0. Literature Review

Artificial intelligence, as the offshoot of information and communication technology powered by computers, is making education and information handling faster and more efficient. It is breaking the paradigms of the past on how to learn and do things in an effective and efficient manner. AI, which is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems (TechTarget, 2024), apart from being astonishing in operations, is a positive force for good in the world. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is an important sub-discipline of computer science. It was first defined during the Dartmouth Conference in 1956 as a technology that can research, develop and create a "brain of machine" that is akin to that of humans and enables machines to think and learn like humans (Nick, 2017).

On the other side, selective dissemination of information (SDI) is seen as an automatic and targeted distribution of information about individuals based on their specific interests and preferences (Saeidnia, 2022). It is a concept rooted in science and information technology and aims to filter and deliver relevant content to users in an efficient manner. Invariably, SDI systems have been developed to deal with the increasing volume of information available and offer personalized information retrieval and delivery. According to Rzhеuskyi, Matsuiк, Veretennikova, and Vaskiv (2018), the first known practical implementation of SDI took place in the 1960s with major contributions from

the online information retrieval community. Institutions such as the US National Library of Medicine (NLM) began experiments using computer systems to automatically disseminate selective information to interested users. One of the most famous and influential systems was the Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System (MEDLARS), introduced by the NLM in 1964. MEDLARS allowed users to define their areas of interest; the system would subsequently notify the stakeholders about new articles matching their criteria (Taine, 1963). This innovative approach was a significant advance in providing personalized information to the scientific community. With the advent of the Internet and the World Wide Web, SDI has evolved significantly. As more information became available online, new techniques and technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) were developed to support efficient filtering and targeted information delivery (Massis, 2018 Kim J, Shin, Bae, Oh, Park & del Pobil, 2020). Innovative platforms integrate various intelligent algorithms, user profiling techniques and automated notifications to increase the effectiveness of SDI systems. Today, noted Saeidnia (2023), the concept of SDI has expanded beyond research and academia. SDI has now been used in business environments, social media platforms, news gathering, and recommender systems using artificial intelligence.

The top five core keywords in studies on AI information dissemination, according to Stahl (2021), are 5G, short video, intellectual media era, media brain, and intellectualization, three of which are related to artificial intelligence and media convergence. Human-machine convergence will be a trend of future development. It is true that progress has been made in developing AI technology along with successful practices in some fields, but its application in information dissemination still needs to be improved. AI for natural language processing systems has already matured by realizing fast text conversion in the processes of information collection, dissemination, and output, saving manpower and material resources and allowing media workers more time to engage in other news businesses. AI news robots can replace human reporters to complete long hours of continuous work with a lower character error rate. The development of big data and algorithms has promoted the efficiency of meeting users' demand with information resources, but the information cocoon cannot be avoided. AI cannot deal with emotions and moods like humans, but the Integration of AI and humans can make up for their respective shortcomings and take advantage of them to facilitate information dissemination. Therefore, in the process of intelligent dissemination, there will be a trend of mutual Integration and synergetic development among human beings and

AI devices. Facing the reform and development of new technologies, we should actively make good use of advanced science and technology.

As asserted by IFLA (2018), librarians are still central to the library's workflow, and AI as a tool is simply designed to complement the librarians' experience and knowledge as a search that is only as good as the search terms put in. In the same vein, Collection HQ (2024) AI can also assist librarians with back-office duties in that computers can now complete regular tasks, such as inventory and catalogue management, holds and reservation management, circulation and check-out and fine notifications and fee collection. It is further stated that the use of virtual assistants and chatbots has also become more commonplace in libraries, acting as a guide for library services and answering frequently asked questions. Having this round-the-clock assistance reduces pressure on library staff, freeing up time to focus on programming and other value-added activities. Indeed, the potential of AI for SDI cannot be underestimated, considering the fact that SDI is a technique that is used to filter and distribute relevant information to individuals based on their specific interests or information needs and going by modus operandi of AI, it remains a veritable tool as it holds significant potential in the selective dissemination of information. It is against this backdrop that Okunlaya, Syed Abdullah and Alias, 2022 asserted that in the age of AI, SDI can be greatly enhanced by leveraging AI technologies and algorithms.

Furthermore, there are indicators of some practical ways AI can be utilized to obtain better SDI performance. These indicators revealed Ramzan, Bajwa, Jamil, Amin, Ramzan, Mirza, et al. (2019), Cui (2021), and Sardinia (2023) include Intelligent Recommendation Systems (IRS) in which AI algorithms can analyze users' preferences, browsing behavior, and historical data to make personalized recommendations and enables SDI systems to deliver highly relevant information to users based on their interests, helping them stay updated on the latest developments in their field. By understanding individual interests and needs, AI can selectively disseminate information that is relevant and engaging for each user (Zhang, Lu & Jin, 2021). In addition posit Piletskiy, Chumachenko and Meniailov (2020), AI, through personalized recommendation systems, create user profiles by collecting and analyzing data such as browsing history, click patterns, purchase history, demographic information, and social media activity, thereby building a comprehensive understanding of each user's preferences, interests, and behaviour.

According to Ayanouz, Abdelhakim, and Benhmed (2020), with advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP), AI can better understand and interpret user queries and information needs and allows SDI systems to provide more accurate and precise information matching the user's requirements, leading to improved content filtering and personalized information retrieval. Contributing in the same vein, Atallah, McDonough, Raskin and Nirenburg (2001) stated that AI algorithms can analyze sentiment and emotions expressed in user-generated content, such as social media posts or reviews. This enables selective dissemination of information based on the sentiment expressed, allowing organizations to respond and engage with users accordingly added Pasupa, Seneewong & Ayutthaya (2022). Through Sentiment analysis, also known as opinion mining which is a technique used in natural language processing (NLP) that involves classifying text into different sentiment categories, such as positive, negative, or neutral, AI can analyze and determine the sentiment or emotion expressed in text data (Petrucci & Dragoni, 2015). This classification said Saberi & Saad (2017) can be performed at different levels of granularity, ranging from binary (positive/negative) to fine-grained scales and in the preprocessing of text data noise such as punctuation, stop words, and special characters are removed and tokenization which is splitting text into individual words or phrases, stemming, the reduction of words to their root form and lemmatization, the reduction words to their base form are carried out.

Another notable way by which AI can enhance SDI performance posit Das, Dey, Pal and Roy (2019) is through Automated Content Classification (ACC) and Contextual Understanding (CU) in which AI techniques like machine learning and text mining can be used to automatically classify and categorize a vast amount of information. This automated content classification (ACC) enables SDI systems to efficiently organize and filter information, making it easier to disseminate relevant content to stakeholders in a timely manner. Also, AI-powered systems can interpret contextual cues, such as location, time, and user context, to deliver timely and location-specific information by so doing, assisting in tailoring the dissemination of information based on the current situation or the user's immediate surroundings (Kadhim, 2019). It is pertinent to state that contextual understanding (CU) is a crucial aspect of AI systems that refers to the ability to interpret and analyze the context in which information is being disseminated or consumed [(Pan et

al., 2022). AI systems revealed by van Berkel, Tag, Goncalves, and Hosio (2022) can leverage location data to provide information that is relevant to a specific geographic location of the user. For instance, a recommendation system for restaurants can take into account the user's current location to suggest nearby dining options. Under SDI, understanding the time or temporal context is important in providing timely and relevant information. To this end, a weather app can consider the current time and date to provide accurate and up-to-date weather forecasts specific to the user's location. The underlying factor is that AI systems can analyze user-specific data, including preferences, demographics, behavior, and past interactions, to personalize information dissemination.

Furtherance write Panda, Upadhyay and Khandelwal (2019) through Intelligent Alert Systems (IAS) and Real-time Information Updates (RtIU) AI-powered alert systems can monitor various sources of information in real-time and deliver notifications to users when new, relevant content becomes available. This, no doubt, is SDI at its best. This Intelligent Alert Systems (IAS), as noted, ensures that users receive up-to-date information that is tailored to their interests and requirements. In addition, AI-powered systems can constantly monitor and analyze vast amounts of data from various sources added Nedelkoski et al (2020) and enables the selective dissemination of real-time information updates (RtIU) on topics of interest, such as news, weather conditions, stock market fluctuations, or sports scores. For clarity's sake, RtIU refers to the timely and immediate SDI as it occurs or is updated in real-time and ensures that users receive the most current and up-to-date information at the time it becomes available (Yates & Kaul, 2019). This is particularly important for time-sensitive data such as news, stock market updates, sports scores, or emergency alerts.

As also revealed, AI can enable SDI systems to learn and adapt to users' preferences over time through so called adaptative learning (AL). Lysyakov (2022) stressed that by analyzing user feedback and interactions, AI algorithms can improve the accuracy of the information provided, continually refining the content selection and matching process and can automatically summarize long-form content or create concise, digestible summaries from large amounts of information. This AI process, indicated by Day and Chen (2018), allows for the selective dissemination of key insights or main points, making it easier for users to consume and comprehend complex

information. It has also been revealed that SDI can be integrated with other AI applications such as chatbots or virtual assistants. These intelligent systems can interact with users, understand their information needs through natural language conversation, and provide personalized information recommendations, enhancing the overall SDI experience. It can be seen that AI technology has been integrated into the process of information dissemination, and the disseminators have changed from humans to smart devices (Chen & Han, 2022). Therefore, AI technology has exerted influence on the source of information dissemination by processing resources from the very beginning and improving the efficiency of information access and accuracy of output.

As we celebrate the gains of AI in enhancing SDI, the truth is that there is another side to the coin, and this other side are the ethical challenges that must be faced in the line of duty as a librarian. These ethical challenges, as listed by Sardinia (2023), include ensuring data privacy, avoiding algorithmic biases, ensuring transparency and accountability of AI systems and addressing concerns related to information overload.

In his contribution toward mitigating the ethical challenges, Stahl (2021) in his book made reference to the importance of ensuring that AI systems (AI ecosystems, in his words) for information dissemination adhere to ethical principles and guidelines. He advised that in as much as it is commonly accepted, AI systems should be transparent in how they select and disseminate information and users should have perfect visibility into the factors and criteria used in the selection process. This is against the backdrop, as hinted by Ouchchy, Coin and Dubljević (2020), that everybody has found cases of quasi-hidden "small characters" or quite unclear promises about "respect of privacy".

In addition, write Stahl, Antoniou, Ryan, Macnish & Jiya (2022), AI algorithms should be explainable, meaning that users should be able to understand why certain information is being recommended or disseminated to them and strive to avoid biases, to dodge vulnerable unawareness, and to ensure fairness in information dissemination. Bias in AI algorithms as they posit can lead to the exclusion or

underrepresentation of certain groups or perspectives therefore efforts should be made to identify and address any biases in the algorithms, ensuring that information dissemination is fair and inclusive. Stahl (2021) stresses the need for AI systems for SDI to give priority to user's privacy and personal information to be handled securely and users to have constant or continuous or even spontaneous control over their data and how it is used. Clear consent mechanisms should be in place to ensure that users understand how their data is being used for selective dissemination of information he suggested.

Siau and Wang (2020) were of the opinion that the organizations and developers behind AI systems should take responsibility for the information being disseminated and be accountable for the impact of their algorithms and address any unintended consequences while Stahl (2021) was of the view that clear mechanisms for user feedback, reporting, and redress should be in place to ensure accountability and that users should have the ability to customize and control their information preferences, filter recommendations and have the option to easily opt-in or out of selective dissemination features as this will ensure that users have agency and choice in the information they receive. Ethical considerations should not be a one-time consideration but an ongoing process he concludes. Siau & Wang (2020) and Stahl (2021) in their final submissions harped on the need for regular monitoring of AI systems for potential biases, privacy violations, or ethical concerns as a necessity as well as feedback from users and external stakeholders to be actively ought to identify areas of improvement and refine the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination.

3.0. Methodology

The study applied a descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 48 special librarians selected through purposive sampling techniques from 24 special libraries in Africa with 2 respondents each which include Nigerian National Assembly Library, Abuja, Central Bank of Nigeria Library, Abuja, Channel Television Library, Lagos, Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) Library, Abuja, Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) Library, Port Harcourt, Nigerian Army Library, Abuja, Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria Library, Abuja, Parliamentary Library of South Africa aka Library of parliament, Johannesburg, South Africa Broadcasting

information needs	27	56.25	12	25	5	1.42	4	8.33	3.30
For timely delivery of CAS	36	75	4	8.33	6	12.5	2	4.17	3.54
To ease the job of special librarians	8	16.66	3	6.25	14	29.17	23	47.92	1.67

Table 1 contains data in respect of the need for AI in special Library for SDI services. From the data the mean value scores for six (6) of the seven (7) items listed in the table were above the benchmark of 2.50 which shows that over 80% of the respondents strongly agree or agree that there is need to apply AI in special libraries in Africa for SDI services. On the other hand, 77.1% representing 37 out of 48 total respondents strongly disagree or disagree that with AI the job of special librarians will be eased.

Table 2: Ways by which AI can enhance SDI services

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
The system builds a comprehensive understanding of each user's preferences, interests, and behavior.	31	64.6	12	25	5	10.4	***	***	3.54
AI algorithms can analyze users' preferences, browsing behavior, and historical data to make personalized recommendations	29	60.42	19	39.58	***	***	***	***	3.60
AI can selectively disseminate information that is relevant and engaging for each user	20	41.67	15	31.25	7	14.6	6	12.5	3.02
AI enables SDI systems to deliver highly relevant information to users based on their interests, helping them stay updated on the latest developments in their field	41	85.4	7	14.6	***	***	***	***	3.85
AI-powered alert systems can monitor various sources of information in real-time and deliver notifications to users when new, relevant content becomes available (CAS)	48	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
AI can enable SDI systems to learn and adapt to users' preferences over time through adaptive learning (AL).	32	66.67	8	16.67	6	12.5	2	4.16	3.46

Data collected and displayed in table 2 reveal that 48 of the respondents or 100% strongly agree that with AI-powered alert systems, various sources of information the library can be monitored in real time and notification delivered to users when new, relevant content becomes available, another 100% of the respondents strongly agree or agree that with AI algorithms, users' preferences, browsing behavior, and historical data to make personalized recommendations can be analyzed and that with AI enables SDI systems, highly relevant information to users based on their interests, helping them stay updated on the latest developments in their field can be delivered, while over 80% of the respondents strongly agree or agree that with AI system, a comprehensive understanding of each user's preferences, interests, and behavior can be built, AI can selectively disseminate information that is relevant and engaging for each user and that AI can enable SDI systems to learn and adapt to users' preferences over time through adaptive learning (AL). As shown in the table the mean value scores range from 3.02 to 4.00 showing high level of acceptance of that with AI, SDI services in special libraries in Africa will tremendously enhanced.

Table 3: Ethical challenges in using AI for SDI

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Data privacy violation	48	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
There is the problem of algorithmic biases as data may not be properly analyzed and AI can potentially amplify existing biases	17	35.4	24	50	6	12.5	1	2.08	3.19
There is the doubt of transparency and accountability of AI systems	37	77.1	11	22.9	***	***	***	***	3.77
AI is not programmed to addressing the problem of information overload	22	45.8	14	29.17	7	14.6	5	10.42	3.10
There is the challenge of refining the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination	31	64.6	9	18.75	7	14.6	1	2.1	3.46
Distribution of harmful content	27	44.57	8	16.67	8	16.67	5	10.42	3.19
Risk of Copyright infringement and legal exposure	26	54.17	13	27.1	2	4.17	7	14.6	3.21

Sensitive information disclosure	4	8.33	11	22.92	23	47.92	10	20.83	2.19
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As shown in table 3, all the respondents which are 48 or 100% strongly agree that the major challenge in using AI for SDI in special libraries in Africa is the issue of data privacy violation, the 100% further strongly agree or agree that there is the problem of transparency and accountability of AI systems. The data further reveal that over 80% of the respondents strongly agree or agree that algorithmic biases, AI not programmed to addressing the problem of information overload, of refining the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination, distribution of harmful content and copyright infringement and legal exposure are all challenges that will be faced in using AI for SDI in special libraries in Africa. The value mean scores that ranged from 3.10 to 4.00 tell of how far the respondents agree to the listed challenges. On the other hand, 68.75% or 33 respondents with a value mean score of 2.19 strongly disagree or disagree on the fat that using AI for SDI will bring about sensitive information disclosure.

Table 4; Steps towards militating challenges in using AI for SDI

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Regular monitoring of AI systems for privacy violation	48	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Regular monitoring of AI systems for potential biases	39	81.25	9	18.75	***	***	***	***	3.81
There should be clear mechanisms for user feedback, reporting, and redress should be in place to ensure accountability	40	83.33	8	16.7	***	***	***	***	3.83
Users should have the ability to customize and control their information preferences, filter recommendations and have the option to easily opt-in or out of selective dissemination features.	37	77.1	11	22.90	***	***	***	***	3.77
Organizations and developers behind AI systems should identify areas of improvement and refine the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination	48	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00

In table 4 above, the data collected and analyzed did show that 48 respondents representing 100% strongly agree that among the ways to mitigate the challenges identified are regular monitoring of AI systems for privacy violation and organizations and developers

behind AI systems identifying areas of improvement and refining the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination. The same 100% either strongly agree or agree that the challenges could be mitigated by creating clear mechanisms for user feedback, reporting, and redress that will ensure accountability, regular monitoring of AI systems for potential biases and users having the ability to customize and control their information preferences, filter recommendations and have the option to easily opt-in or out of selective dissemination features. The mean scores range from 3.77 to 4.00, an indication of strong agreement to the solutions.

5.0. Discussion of Findings

The outcome of this study as displayed in table 1 did reveal that there is need for AI to be used for SDI in special libraries in Africa. As shown in table 1 it needed for any reason which include to make up inadequacy of staff, to meet up with information needs of the teeming users, to enhance efficiency of service, for effective SDI, for proper and accurate identification of individual information needs and for timely delivery of CAS. This result is an affirmation of the assertion that SDI is a technique that is used to filter and distribute relevant information to individuals based on their specific interests or information needs and going by modus operandi of AI, it remains a veritable tool as it holds significant potential in the selective dissemination of information therefore in this age of AI, SDI can be greatly enhanced by leveraging AI technologies and algorithms (Okunlaya, Syed, Abdullah & Alias, 2022). In the contrary, it was found that with AI being used for SDI in special libraries in Africa as asserted will ease the job of special librarians was refuted. The reason may not be far from IFLA (2018) stand that Librarians are still central to the library's workflow and AI as a tool is simply designed to complement the librarians' experience and knowledge noting that a search is only as good as the search terms put in.

The study also discovered that there are any ways special libraries in Africa can leverage AI to enhance the SDI services (see table 2). From the result, with AI-powered alert systems, various sources of information in the library can be monitored in real time and notification delivered to users when new, relevant content becomes available. With AI algorithms, users' preferences, browsing behavior, and historical data to make personalized recommendations can be analyzed and that with AI enables SDI systems, highly relevant

information to users based on their interests, helping them stay updated on the latest developments in their field can be delivered. Furtherance with AI system, a comprehensive understanding of each user's preferences, interests, and behavior can be built, AI can also selectively disseminate information that is relevant and engaging for each user and that AI can enable SDI systems to learn and adapt to users' preferences over time through adaptive learning (AL).

This result collaborates Ramzan, Bajwa, Jamil, Amin, Ramzan, Mirza, et al (2019), Cui (2021) and Saeidnia (2023) who revealed that with Intelligent Recommendation Systems (IRS) AI algorithms can analyze users' preferences, browsing behavior, and historical data to make personalized recommendations and enables SDI systems to deliver highly relevant information to users based on their interests, helping them stay updated on the latest developments in their field. By understanding individual interests and needs and Zhang, Lu & Jin, (2021) who noted that AI can selectively disseminate information that is relevant and engaging for each user among other authors.

The study further discovered that there are many ethical challenges that special libraries in Africa will fight against or avoid while using AI in SDI. According to the finding one major challenge in using AI for SDI in special libraries in Africa is that of data privacy violation, while others include transparency and accountability of AI systems, algorithmic biases, AI not programmed to addressing the problem of information overload, of refining the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination as well as distribution of harmful content and copyright infringement and legal exposure.

This result is in tandem with the ethical challenges listed by Saeidnia, (2023) which include, ensuring data privacy violation, algorithmic biases, problem of transparency and accountability of AI systems and information overload. On the other hand, using AI for SDI that is believed will bring about sensitive information disclosure was found not to be a challenge. This may be attributed to the fact that information retrieved by special librarians as professional are not released hook, line and sinker to the user rather it is always vetted before being given out to the final user.

Furtherance, it was also found that there are ways to mitigate the ethical challenges identified. Among the ways as shown in table 4 are regular monitoring of AI systems for privacy violation and organizations and developers behind AI systems identifying areas of improvement and refining the algorithms and processes of selective dissemination as well as creating clear mechanisms for user feedback, reporting, and redress that will ensure accountability, regular monitoring of AI systems for potential biases and users having the ability to customize and control their information preferences, filter recommendations and have the option to easily opt-in or out of selective dissemination features.

This result is in agreement with Stahl (2021) who in his book made reference to the importance of ensuring that AI systems (AI ecosystems, in his words) for information dissemination adhere to ethical principles and guidelines. He advised that in as much as it is commonly accepted, AI systems should be transparent in how they select and disseminate information and users should have perfect visibility into the factors and criteria used in the selection process and also Ouchchy, Coin and Dubljević (2020) revealed that everybody has found cases of quasi hidden “small characters” or quite unclear promises about “respect of privacy”. Stahl (2021) also stresses the need for AI systems for SDI to give priority to user’s privacy and personal information to be handled securely and users to have constant or continuous or even spontaneous control over their data and how it is used. Clear consent mechanisms should be in place to ensure that users understand how their data is being used for selective dissemination of information he suggested. Others whose works are unison with this finding include Siau & Wang (2020) and Stahl, Antoniou, Ryan, Macnish & Jiya (2022).

5.1. Conclusion and Recommendations

From traditional printing media to AI information dissemination, disseminating modes as experienced have undergone substantial changes. Instead of single information dissemination, audiences are requiring diversified and valid information more than ever.

Combining with AI technology, major information dissemination platforms can identify individual needs of users, filter and push messages to users more accurately and precisely. The biggest advantage of AI in information dissemination as found out in this study is that it can analyze and screen users' habits through data sharing and meet individual needs of personalized dissemination. In the era of AI technology, however, librarians especially special librarians should avoid algorithm bias and comply with the rules of data sharing. They should also rationally understand that utilizing the power of AI technology can complement the shortcomings of human beings, but potential risks in AI devices should be well-controlled. To sum up, Special librarians should make proper use of AI technology to help us spread information efficiently through SDI and CAS. Be that as it may, no matter the way it is looked at, research has shown that AI is an asset to special libraries and librarians thus librarians have significant role to play as AI can also play critical role in helping special librarians by extension other librarians make key decisions that will impact the future of the library. In this regard, the following recommendations are made;

- With AI technology continuing to become more prevalent, special librarians are also required to educate library users on Artificial Intelligence and how it can enhance their daily life. After all, AI transforms the world can only be established when it is used.
- It is true that there are these concerns that increased use of AI in SDI could lead to the spread of disinformation and misinformation, not to mention security and privacy issues. Librarians in special libraries in Africa can play a pivotal role in championing the responsible use of AI and must learn how to discern AI-generated text and images to pass these skills on to users.
- The spread of Artificial Intelligence certainly brings with it a combination of exciting opportunity and change. With forethought, planning and consideration of the risks, special libraries in Africa can ensure they are not only prepared for the changes that AI is bringing but that they are also positioned to shape and then lead the world that AI is helping to create.. This can be achieved by special librarians and staff of the library if they are regularly trained and re-trained in line with the emerging technology by management of parent institutions who are financiers of the library.

- AI can certainly enhance SDI in special libraries in Africa but special librarians and staff of special libraries in Africa must also be mindful of the ethical implications of using AI in SDI service delivery and take steps to protect the privacy and ownership of data. The underscored fact is that while AI has the potential to enhance SDI in these libraries, special libraries should proceed with caution and consider its potential negative impact. By being mindful of these concerns and taking steps to mitigate them by ensuring that AI is used in a responsible and ethical manner that benefits both the library and users.
- Special libraries in Africa should come together to establish African Special Libraries Consortium (ASLC) with which they can bargain collectively and aggressively reduced costs for the libraries access to AI technology, share their thoughts and experiences in the utilization of AI technology in general service and SDI in particular as well as exchange of ideas and skills.

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2.The Impact of AI on Information Dissemination Patterns

There are three important elements in the process of information dissemination: disseminator, media and audience. AI technology has penetrated into these elements to enable a faster and more effective information dissemination. With the emergence of AI, each element is getting more intelligent.

2.1 AI's Impact on Disseminators

As the trigger of information dissemination, disseminators can get more information resources with the help of AI technology. In this process, information resources are mainly recognized and collected by a human being, whose ability is relatively limited. AI technology, however, can make up for the limitation as it can not only collect information from many aspects and channels but also complete data analysis and processing within the shortest time. For information collection, intelligent devices can acquire voices and images that cannot be recognized by a human being. Intelligent devices are becoming more popular than ever in news reporting because they can collect graphics, articles, and sound and convert these resources into text. During the National Two Sessions in 2021, new AI products such as IFlyTEK Smart Office X2 were adopted to help journalists efficiently collect information on-site and convert them into manuscripts for reporting. It can be seen that AI technology has been integrated into the process of information dissemination, and the disseminators have changed from humans to smart devices. Therefore, AI technology has exerted influence on the source of information dissemination by processing resources from the very beginning and improving the efficiency of information access and accuracy of output.

2.2AI'sImpact on Media

From print media to electronic media and digital media, the media of information dissemination has gone through three eras. With the synchronous development of economy, culture and science, substantial changes have occurred in dissemination media. The traditional concept of media no longer exists. After AI technology emerged, it redefined the media of information dissemination. A new form brought by AI has made the media more immersive. Hardware media have become a widely-accepted information carrier. Being integrated with AI, machinery equipment has been upgraded and enabled to act as media to work and transmit information like humans. In the age of AI, intelligent machines and devices have become parts of our lives, and media immersion is inevitable. AI is not yet as emotional as a human being, but it has become a perfect tool to help people collect and organize data. With the development of technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR), and holographic imaging, media of information dissemination have also expanded.

2.3AI'sImpact onAudience

AI's impact on the audience is mainly embodied in the forms of the final presentation of information and the experience of the audience. The adoption of AI technology mainly aims to improve audience's perception of the content being disseminated. AI technology can help tackle the problems such as information barrier and asymmetry in the process of information dissemination. The major impact of AI in this www.scholink.org/ojs/index.php/asir Applied Science and Innovative respect focuses on improving users' experience. The fire at Notre Dame Cathedral in Paris on April 15, 2019 helped promote the application of AI technology in protecting and inheriting cultural heritage. Today, an increasing number of tourists can travel around the world via live streaming or visit scenic spots via smart devices. Xinhua News Agency developed a 2D AI Virtual Anchor in 2018along with Sogou, Inc., and launched its 3D version in the following years. In 2021, Xinhua News Agency introduced a smart studio that allowed the free switching of multiple scenes during the National Two Sessions. AI Anchors can efficiently complete information collection and output with relatively small errors and improve audience experience. With the development of science and technology, people are paying more attention to the visualization of news. Transforming media of information dissemination from screen into a virtual scene allows the audience to experience the on-site atmosphere, truly understand and feel the situations of news, and bring a greater sense of immersion to users.

3.Exploring the Development Trend of AI Information Dissemination

In the literature related to AI information dissemination, the repetition and highly-frequent occurrence of a keyword means that it has been the hotspot of the research field. In this research, CiteSpace software was used to take keywords as analysis units, the time slice was set to 1, the threshold was set to 50, and the keyword co-occurrence map was formed, as shown in Figure 1.

The diameter of node circle represents the frequency of occurrence of keywords. The larger the diameter is, the higher the frequency is. The font size of keywords represents the different degree of importance. The larger the font size, the more important and central it is. In previous studies, algorithms, big data, media convergence, intelligent communication, etc., are all high-frequency hotspots in the research field of AI information dissemination.

Figure 1. Contribution Diagram of Keywords in AI Information Dissemination Research www.scholink.org/ojs/index.php/asir Applied Science and Innovative Research Vol. 6, No. 1, 2022

The “Time Zone View” function of CiteSpace was used to draw the map of hot Time Zones of AI information dissemination research from 1999 to 2020 (as shown in Figure 2), which shows the keywords with high frequency and rapid growth in different periods in this research field. By summarizing the keywords and the combined cluster identifiers, it can be found that there are three major future trends in the research on AI information dissemination.

Figure 2. TimeZone View of Hot Spots in AI Information Dissemination Research

Table 1. Keywords of the Previous Studies on AI Information Dissemination

Dissemination keyword	frequency	Year of first occurrence
artificial intelligence	326	1999
Media convergence	73	2016
big data	54	1999
algorithm	32	2017
Smart media	32	2008
Intelligent technology	27	1999
information	26	1999
5g	24	2018
Short video	22	2018
Intelligent communication	22	2017
News production	21	2017
Smart media	20	2017
Public opinion governance	20	1999
Intellectual Media Era	20	2018
National Governance	19	1999
journalism	19	2016
Governance	18	1999
Innovation		
new media	18	2016

Media brain	17	2018
Intellectualization	17	2018
media industry	17	2008
News	15	2018
communication		
All media	14	2018
Algorithm	13	2018
recommendation		
Content production	12	2017
mainstream media	11	2018
Journalistic ethics	11	2018
Media integration	11	2017
Social media	10	2015
Xinhua News	10	2018
Agency		
Traditional media	10	2016

3.1 Human-machine Integration

It can be seen from Table 1 that in 2018, the top five core keywords in studies on AI information dissemination are 5G, short video, intellectual media era, media brain and intellectualization, three of which are related to artificial intelligence and media convergence. Human-machine convergence will be a trend of future development. Although progress has been made in developing AI technology along with successful practices in some fields, its application in information dissemination still needs to be improved. AI for natural language processing systems has already matured by realizing fast text conversion in the processes of information collection, dissemination, and output, saving manpower and material resources and allowing media workers more time to engage in other news businesses. AI news robots can replace human reporters to complete long hours of continuous work with lower character error rate. The development of big data and algorithms has promoted the efficiency of meeting users' demand with information resources, but information cocoon cannot be avoided. AI cannot deal with emotions and moods like humans, but the integration of AI and humans can make up for their respective shortcomings and take advantage of them to facilitate information dissemination. Therefore, in the process of intelligent dissemination, there will be a trend of mutual integration and synergetic development among human beings and AI devices. Facing the reform and development of new technologies, we should actively make good use of advanced science and technology.

Data Sharing Mechanism

It can be seen from Figure 2 that one of the research hotspots of AI information dissemination will be “algorithm ethics”, indicating that the development of AI in the future is unstoppable, and it is necessary to establish algorithm ethics to restrain possible problems in data sharing. “With the proposition of absolute data

sharing, data conflicts with rights-based data ethics that supports data sharing but opposes the behaviour of sharing data without respecting individual rights or in a disorderly and unrestrained manner" (Li, 2018). Any disseminator should guarantee data privacy and obtain informed consent from each user before collecting and analyzing their personal data so as to avoid algorithmic bias, which has attracted increasing attention in society. For example, the price of riding a car via DiDi to the same dropping point may vary for users of different mobiles; that is to say, the price for iPhone users is higher than that of Huawei users. In the era of AI, major network platforms and APP platforms should comply with relevant management rules and reasonably collect and use users' data on the basis of a data sharing mechanism. At present, many organizations are working to realize data sharing, and at the same time, many data protection systems have been developed to ensure that science and technology are benefiting human beings.

3.3 Virtual Technology

It can be seen from Figure 1 that algorithms, big data, media convergence, and intelligent communication are all high-frequency hot spots of the research on AI information dissemination, and that AI is changing our lives as well as the presentation modes of the elements of information dissemination. Early in 2017, the Associated Press mentioned AI's role in newspaper business in *the Artificial Intelligence Playbook* and stated that the combination of AI and VR would be the development trend of future technologies. AI and VR are quite different: the former is mainly adopted to contextualize visual and auditory effects for human beings. In the near future, VR technology will improve the experience of news audiences, for example, allows them to experience the virtual scenes of disasters. The effect of information dissemination with VR technology will be much improved. In addition, the technology can also connect and reconstruct time and space for the audience to get an overlapped and immersive experience. The immersive mode can avoid the bias of information dissemination. The rapid development of AI technology enables the combination of virtuality and reality in the process of information dissemination and allows the audience to receive the main information in a more real and effective way.

4. Conclusion

From traditional printing media to AI information dissemination, the dissemination modes we have experienced have undergone substantial changes. Instead of single information dissemination, audiences require more diversified and valid information than ever before. Combined with AI technology, major information dissemination platforms can identify the individual needs of users and filter and push messages to users more accurately and precisely. The biggest advantage of AI in information dissemination is that it can analyze and screen users' habits through data sharing and meet individual needs of personalized dissemination. In the era of AI technology, however, we should avoid algorithm bias and comply with the rules of data sharing. we should also rationally understand that utilizing the power of AI technology can complement the shortcomings of human beings, but potential risks in AI devices should be well-controlled. To sum up, we should make proper use of AI technology to help us spread information efficiently.

Fund Information

Guangxi "Bagui Scholars" Construction Project; Supported by high Level Innovation Team project of Guangxi Universities

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